

**A new subspecies of *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) talyschense*
Ganglbauer, 1884 from Iran (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)**

M.A. Lazarev

State Budget Professional Educational Institution of the Moscow Region
“Chekhov technical college”

Novaya str., 4, Novyy Byt village, Chekhov District, Moscow Region 142322 Russia

e-mail: cerambycidae@fromru.com; humanityspace@gmail.com

Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Dorcadionini, *Dorcadion*, taxonomy, new subspecies, Iran, Azerbaijan.

Abstract: *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) talyschense sabalanum* ssp. n. is described from North Iran, Ardebil province, SE slope of Sabalan Mt.

A big series of *Dorcadion talyschense*, collected by S. Murzin in North Iran was recognized as a new subspecies and described below. So, the species consists now of 2 subspecies.

Several abbreviations are used in the text:

MD - collection of M. Danilevsky (Moscow, Russia)

ML - collection of M. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia)

NHMW - collection of Naturhistorisches Museum Wien (Austria)

SM - collection of S. Murzin (Moscow, Russia)

ZMM - collection of Zoological Museum of Moscow State University (Moscow, Russia)

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) talyschense talyschense Ganglbauer, 1884

Figs 1-8; Map 1

Dorcadion (s. str.) *plasoni* var. *talyschense* Ganglbauer, 1884: 491 - “bei Rasano im Gebiete des caspischen Meeres”.

Dorcadion talyschense var. *posticeinterruptum* Pic, 1900: 12 - “Caucase”.

Dorcadion talyschense ab. *posticeinterruptum*, Aurivillius, 1922: 30 - “Transkaukasien”; Winkler, 1929: 1194 - “Ca.”.

Dorcadion (s. str.) *talyschense*, Aurivillius, 1922: 30 - “Lenkoran, Talysch-Gebirge”; Winkler, 1929: 1194 - “Lenk.”; Plavilstshikov, 1932: 193 - Transcaucasie.

Dorcadion (Autodorcadion) talyschense Plavilstshikov, 1958: 234, part. (unjustified emendation) - Azerbaijan: Talysh part of Mugan; North-

M.A. Lazarev

West of Iran: Iranian Talysh, Gilan, north-east and east of Iranian Azerbaijan; Lobanov et al., 1982: 263; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 327, 332, part. - south-east Azerbaijan, common in Diabar depression, North Iran.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) talyschense, Breuning, 1958: 31, part. - "Talysh, Perse"; 1962: 477, part. - "vom Ufer des Kaspischen Meeres: Rasano", "Persien: Mts. Elburs, von Zendjan nach Ardebil", "Talysh".

Dorcadion talyschense, Danilevsky, 1986: 68 (endangered species).

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) talyschense, Danilevsky et al., 2005: 137 (endophallus); Danilevsky & Murzin, 2009: 3, part. - "Azerbajdzhan, mountain steppe of Talysh ridge - Zuvand area; Iran: Azerbajdzhan - Iranian part of Talysh ridge, Mt. Sabalan and Nur Lake; Nir environs; 26 km westwards Nir"; Danilevsky, 2010: 254.

Dorcadion talyschense, Holzschuh, 2007: 249.

Type locality. Azerbaijan, Talysh, Zuvand, Rasano (now ruins in about 5 km westwards from Gasmalyan, 38°40'12"N, 48°18'46"E).

Diagnosis. The nominative subspecies is characterised by moderately rough pronotal punctation, usually without rugae; most of dots are usually not conjugated; humeral carinae less exposed with less rough sculpture; dorsal elytral furrows less pronounced; body light pubescens always white, never yellowish; body length in males: 12.7-16.6 mm, width: 4.5-6.5 mm; body length in females: 15.0-19.3 mm, width: 6.5-7.8 mm.

Materials. Lectotype (figs 1-2), present desination, with three labels:

- 1) "*Dorcadion / talyschense /* Ganglb. Süant. / Caspi-Meer.";
 - 2) "TYPUS";
 - 3) "LECTOTYPUS / *Dorcadion* (s. str.) *plasoni* var. / *TALYSCHENSE /* Ganglbauer, 1884 / M.Lazarev des., 2017 - NHMW;
- 1 male with two labels: 1) "Talysh", 2) "*D. / talyschense /* Gglb. / det. N. Plavilstshikov" - ZMM;
- 1 male with three labels: 1) "Talyshgeb. / Transcaucas / Leder, Reitter", 2) "type 200", 3) "*D. / talyschense /* Gglb. / det. N. Plavilstshikov"- ZMM;
- 1 male with two labels: 1) "Talyshgeb. / Transcaucas / Leder, Reitter", 2) "*D. / talyschense /* Gglb. / det. N. Plavilstshikov" - ZMM;
- 1 females with three labels: 1) a. "Caucas. Talysh.", b. "Reitter", 2) "*D. talyschense /* Gglb. / ab. *posticeinter - / riptum* Pic / det. N. Plavilstshikov", 3) "*Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) / talyschense /*

M.A. Lazarev

TALYSCHENSE / Ganglbauer, 1884 / M.Lazarev det., 2017” - ZMM; 1 female with two labels: 1) “Talysh”, 2) “*D. talyshense* Gglb. / m. ♀ *ardebiense* / Pic / det. N. Plavilstshikov” - ZMM; 1 male with three labels: 1) “typus”, 2) “cont. / Persiae / Step. Mugan.” 3) “*D. talyshense* / Gglb / ab. *praeligatum* / m / N. Plavilstshikov det. / 1939” - ZMM; 1 male, Azerbaijan, Gasmalyan, 30.5.1974, V.Murzin - SM; 7 males, 13 females, Az.SSR, Gasmalyan, 31.5. 1979, 2.6.1979, 8.4.1980, 18.4.1980, 20.5.1980, 22.5.1980 M.Danilevsky leg. - MD, ML, SM; 3 males, Azerbaijan, Zuvand, Gili-Dara, 10.5.1971, V.Murzin - SM; 1 male, Azerbaidzhan, Talysh Mts., Gili-Dara, 20.5.1986, V.Zimberov - MD; 60 males, Azerbaidzhan, Talysh, Zuvand, 21.4-9.5.1988, A.Chuvilin - MD, ML; 1 male, Talysh mts, Zuvand, 1200 m, 15.5.1989 - SM; 2 females, Talysh, Yardymly, 1700 m, 13.5.2014 - MD.

Distribution. South-East Azerbaijan, Talysh Mountains; known localities are: Rasano (now ruins in about 5 km westwards from Gasmalyan, about 38°40'12"N, 48°18'46"E), Gasmalyan environs (about 38°40'22"N, 48°22'15"E), Gili-Dara (about 38°42'4"N, 48°18'43"E, 5 km NW Gasmalyan); Yardymly environs (about 38°54'30"N, 48°14'32"E); Iranian part of Talysh Mountains.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) talyschense sabalanum* ssp. n.**

Figs 9-19, Map 1

Dorcadion talyschense var. *morgani* Pic, 1905: 301 - “plateau persan occidental” (unavailable name - two names proposed for one population); Aurivillius, 1922: 30 - “Persien“; Winkler, 1929: 1194 - “Pers.”.

Dorcadion talyschense var. *ardebiense* Pic, 1905: 301 - plateau persan occidental” (unavailable name - two names proposed for one population).

Dorcadion talyschense ab. *ardebiense*, Aurivillius, 1922: 30 - “Persien“; Winkler, 1929: 1194 - “Pers.”.

Dorcadion (Autodorcadion) talyschense Plavilstshikov, 1958: 234, part. (unjustified emendation) - Azerbaijan: Talysh part of Mugan; “North-West of Iran: Iranian Talysh, Gilan, north-east and east of Iranian Azerbaijan”; Lobanov et al., 1982: 263; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 327, 332, part. - south-east Azerbaijan, common in Diabar depression, North Iran.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) talyschense, Breuning, 1958: 31, part. -

M.A. Lazarev

“Talysh, Perse”; 1962: 477, part. - “vom Ufer des Kaspischen Meeres: Rasano”, “Persien: Mts. Elburs, von Zendjan nach Ardebil“, “Talysh“.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) talyshense, Danilevsky & Murzin, 2009b: 3 - “Azerbajdzhan, mountain steppe of Talysh ridge - Zuvand area; Iran: Azerbajdzhan - Iranian part of Talysh ridge, Mt. Sabalan and Nur Lake; Nir environs; 26 km westwards Nir”.

Type locality. Iran, Ardebil province, SE slope of Sabalan Mt., 11.5 km W Sarein, 38°8'24"N, 47°56'24"E, 2081 m.

Diagnosis. Pronotal punctation very rough, usually strongly rugose with conjugated dots; humeral carinae strongly exposed usually with very rough sculpture, granulated; dorsal elytral furrows better pronounced; body light pubescens sometimes yellowish; body length in males: 12.3-16.8 mm, width: 4.8-6.4 mm; body length in females: 13.9-20.7 mm, width: 6.0-8.0 mm.

The diagnostic characters of the new subspecies were adequately described by Pic (1905) for his var. *ardebienne* and var. *morgani*.

Materials. Holotype (figs 9-10), male with two labels: 1) “Iran / Ardebil prov. 23.04.2001 / SE slope of Sabalan Mt. / 11.5 km W Sarein 2081 m / 38°8'24"N, 47°56'24"E / S.Murzin leg.”, 2) “HOLOTYPUS / *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) talyshense* / *SABALANUM* ssp. n. / M.Lazarev det., 2017” - ML; 132 paratypes; 122 males, 18 females, from same locality - MD, ML, SM, ZMM; 1 male with three labels: 1) “Ardebil / lac. Sali, 3.IV.1912”, 2) “*D. talyshense* Gglb. / ab. *morgani* Pic / det. N. Plavilstshikov”, 3) “PARATYPUS / *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) talyshense* / *SABALANUM* ssp. n. / M.Lazarev det., 2017” - ZMM.

Distribution. North-western Iran: south-east slope of Sabalan Mt., 11.5 km W Sarein, 38°8'24"N, 47°56'24"E, 2081 m; Nir environs (about 38°2'N, 48°E), 1750 m (Danilevsky & Murzin, 2009b); Nur lake (about 38°N, 48°33'E), 2500 m (Danilevsky & Murzin, 2009b).

Remark. *Pedestredorcadion talyshense* m. *latevittipenne* Breuning, 1974: 133 was described on the base of a single male (identified by Breuning as a female) from “Lac de Nur”. The specimen was published as a holotype of *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) nurense* Danilevsky & Murzin, 2009a.

M.A. Lazarev

Acknowledgements. I am very grateful to Mikhail Danilevsky (Moscow, Russia), Sergey Murzin (Moscow, Russia), Aleksey Gusakov and Andrey Ozerov (Zoological Museum of Moscow State University, Moscow, Russia), Andrey Lobanov (Zoological Institute, Saint-Petersburg, Russia), my sincere thanks to Harald Schillhammer (Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, Austria) for the photographs of the type of *Dorcadion plasoni* var. *talyschense* Ganglb. and its labels.

REFERENCES

- Aurivillius C. 1922. Cerambycidae: Lamiinae I. Pars 73. In: Schenkling S. (ed.). Coleopterorum Catalogus. Volumen XXIII. Cerambycidae II. [1921]. Berlin: W. Junk, 322 pp.
- Breuning S. 1958. 1. Lieferung, pp: 1-48. In: S.Breuning, 1958-1969. Catalogue des Lamiaires du Monde (Col. Céramb.). Tutzing bei München, Verlag des Museums G.Frey. 1069 pp.
- Breuning S. 1962. Revision der Dorcadionini (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). - Entomologische Abhandlungen und Berichte aus dem Staatlichen Museum für Tierkunde in Dresden. 27: 1-665.
- Breuning S. & Villiers A. 1974. Trois nouveaux longicornes d'Iran. - L'Entomologist. 33(3): 131-133.
- Danilevsky M.L. 1986. [Rare timber-beetles species (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) in Transcaucasia and problem of their protection. - 1st Transcaucasian conference on Entomology (thesis of reports), Erevan]: 68-69. [in Russian]
- Danilevsky M.L. 2010. tribe Dorcadionini, pp. 241-264. - In I. Löbl & A. Smetana (ed.): Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera, Vol. 6. Stenstrup: Apollo Books, 924 pp.
- Danilevsky M.L., Miroshnikov A.I., 1985. [Timber-Beetles of Caucasus (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). Key. - Krasnodar: "Kubanskiy Selskokhozyaystvennyi Institut"]. 419 pp. [in Russian]
- Danilevsky M.L. & Murzin S. V., 2009a. A revue of *Dorcadion* Dalman, 1817 species of "laeve-group". Part 1 (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Lamiinae). - Les cahiers Magellanes. 92: 1-20.
- Danilevsky M.L. & Murzin S. V., 2009b. A revue of *Dorcadion* Dalman, 1817 species of "laeve-group". Part 2 (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Lamiinae). - Les cahiers Magellanes. 93: 1-22.
- Lobanov A.L., Danilevsky M.L., Murzin S.V. 1982. Systematic list of longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of the USSR. 2. - Revue d'Entomology. 61 (2): 252-277.
- Pic M. 1905. Diagnoses de longicornes asiatiques recueillis par M. J. de Morgan.- Bulletin du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle de Paris. 11: 300-301.
- Plavilstshikov N.N. 1932. Timber-beetles - Timber Pests. Moscow, Leningrad: "Gosudarstvennoe Lesnoe Tekhnicheskoe Izdatelstvo". 200 pp. [in Russian]
- Plavilstshikov N.N. 1958. Faune de l'URSS. Insects Coléoptères. 23(1). Cerambycidae (P.3). Sous-famille Lamiinae, p.1. Moscou, Leningrad:

M.A. Lazarev

“Izdatelstvo Akademii Nauk SSSR”. 592 pp. [in Russian]
Winkler A. 1929. Cerambycidae. Pars 9: 1135-1136; pars 10: 1137-1226. - In:
Catalogus Coleopterorum regionis palaearticae. Wien: A. Winkler Verlag,
1698 pp.

Figs 1-2. *Dorcadion* (*Cribridorcadion*) *talyschense talyschense* Ganglbauer, 1884:

1-2 - Lectotype, present designation, male with three labels:
1) “*Dorcadion* / *talyschense* / Ganglb. Süant. / Caspi-Meer.”;
2) “TYPUS”; 3) “LECTOTYPUS / *Dorcadion* (s. str.) *plasoni* var. / *TALYSCHENSE* / Ganglbauer, 1884 / M.Lazarev des., 2017”. Foto by H.Schillhammer.

Figs 3-8. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) talyschense talyschense* Ganglbauer, 1884: 3 - male, Az.SSR, Gasmalyan, 20.5.1980, M.Danilevsky leg.; 4 - male, Az.SSR, Gasmalyan, 2.6.1979, M.Danilevsky leg.; 5-6 - female with three labels: 1) a. "Caucas. Talysch.", b. "Reitter", 2) "*D. talyschense* Ggbl. / ab. *posticeinter-ruptum* Pic / det. N. Plavilstshikov", 3) "*Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) / talyschense / TALYSCHENSE / Ganglbauer, 1884 / M.Lazarev det., 2017*"; 7 - female, Az.SSR, Gasmalyan, 22.5.1980, M.Danilevsky leg.; 8 - female, Az.SSR, Gasmalyan, 18.4.1980, M.Danilevsky leg.

Iran, Ardebil prov. 23.04.2001
SE slope of Sabalan Mt.
11.5 km W Sarein 2081m
38° 8'24"N, 47°56'24"E
S.Murzin leg.

HOLOTYPUS
Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion)
talyschense
SABALANUM ssp. n.
M.Lazarev det., 2017

10

11

12

13

Figs 9-13. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) talyschense sabalanum* ssp. n.: 9-10 - Holotype, male with two labels: 1) "Iran / Ardebil prov. 23.04.2001 / SE slope of Sabalan Mt. / 11.5 km W Sarein 2081 m / 38°8'24"N, 47°56'24"E / S.Murzin leg.", 2) "HOLOTYPUS / *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion)* / *talyschense* / *SABALANUM* ssp. n. / M.Lazarev det., 2017"; 11-13 - Paratypes, males, from same locality.

Figs 14-19. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) talyschense sabalanum* ssp. n.:
14 - Paratype, male, Iran, Ardebil province, SE slope of Sabalan Mt.,
11.5 km W Sarein, 38°8'24"N, 47°56'24"E, 2081 m, 23.04.2001,
S.Murzin leg; 15-16 - Paratype, male with three labels: 1) "Ardebil /
lac. Sali, 3.IV.1912", 2) "*D. talyschense* Gglb. / ab. *morgani* Pic / det.
N. Plavilstshikov", 3) "PARATYPUS / *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion)*
/ *talyschense* / *SABALANUM* ssp. n. / M.Lazarev det., 2017; 17-19 -
Paratypes, females, Iran, Ardebil province, SE slope of Sabalan Mt.,
11.5 km W Sarein, 38°8'24"N, 47°56'24"E, 2081 m, 23.04.2001,
S.Murzin leg.

Map 1. *D. (C.) t. talyschense* Ganglbauer, 1884 (1-4), *D. (C.) t. sabalanum ssp. n.* (5-7):

Azerbaijan: 1 - Rasano (38°40'12"N, 48°18'46"E); 2 - Gasmalyan environs (38°40'22"N, 48°22'15"E); 3 - Gili-Dara (38°42'4"N, 48°18'43"E); 4 - Yardymly environs (38°54'30"N, 48°14'32"E).

Iran, Ardebil province: 5 - south-east slope of Sabalan Mt., 11.5 km W Sarein, 38°8'24"N, 47°56'24"E, 2081 m; 6 - Nir environs (about 38°2'N, 48°E), 1750 m; 7 - Nur lake (about 38°N, 48°33'E), 2500 m.

Received: 18.05.2017

Accepted: 19.06.2017